

MODE I AND MODE II FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF MENDABLE HYBRID 3D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel three-dimensional (3D) hybrid textile composite that uniquely combines high resistance to mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture with the capacity to *in-situ* repair delamination cracks. The 3D hybrid textile composite contains two types of through-thickness z-binder reinforcements made of carbon fibre tows (which provide high resistance to delamination cracking) and thermoplastic filaments (which provide the capability to heal delamination cracks). The interlaminar fracture properties of this 3D hybrid composite is compared with 3D textile composites containing only one of the two z-binders, and a 2D composite without any z-binders. The hybrid z-binder reinforcements increase the mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness by ~1200% and ~75%, respectively, compared to the 2D composite. The hybrid z-binders simultaneously enable the healing functionality for *in-situ* repair of delamination cracks leading to partial recovery of the interlaminar fracture toughness properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

An effective method for improving the delamination resistance of fibre-polymer composites is through-the-thickness reinforcement using high stiffness and strength fibres to form three dimensionally (3D) reinforced material [1]. 3D fibre composites consist of warp and weft yarns to provide high in-plane mechanical properties together with through-thickness z-binder yarns to provide high interlaminar fracture toughness. The z-binder yarns are usually inserted by weaving, stitching, tufting or z-pinning in a repeating pattern [2-8], and their volume content can be adjusted (typically 0.5 to 5-10%) via the pitch and spacing. 3D fibre composites possess higher interlaminar fracture toughness and fatigue resistant properties compared to 2D laminates due to the through-thickness z-binders. However, a long standing issue with through-thickness reinforced composites is the high-cost repair of damage which is typically caused by impact, over-loading, fatigue loading or environmental degradation. The damaged material must usually be repaired by patching over the damaged region (although the crack remains) or by scarf repair (replacing the defective material) [9]; with both repair methods being labour intensive and slow. A novel approach is to repair the damage *in-situ* within the 3D fibre composite by modifying the fabric and/or the polymer matrix phase. When damage occurs, the healing process can be self-activated or activated using external stimuli (e.g. heat) to repair the 3D composite and restore the mechanical properties [10, 11]. This paper presents an experimental investigation into a hybrid 3D woven composite material that combines high delamination resistance with *in-situ* repair functionality.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The carbon fibre-epoxy composites investigated in this study comprised of plain woven T300 carbon fabric. Stacks of the woven fabric were manually woven in an orthogonal through-thickness pattern using carbon tow or mendable thermoplastic filament of polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid (EMMA) or a combination of both reinforcements, as shown schematically in Figure 1. The 3D woven fabrics were then infused with epoxy resin using the vacuum bag resin infusion technique. The mode I and II interlaminar fracture toughness properties of the various types of 3D composite materials were measured

using the double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notched flexure (ENF) tests, respectively. To prevent the sub-laminate arms of the DCB and ENF specimens from breaking during testing, due to the greatly improved fracture toughness, they were strengthened with two 15-ply unidirectional carbon fibre-epoxy composite tabs, which were externally bonded to the specimens.

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness was calculated using the modified beam theory in accordance with ASTM D5528 using the following expression:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta_I}{2B(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

where P denotes the applied force, δ_I the crack opening displacement, a the total crack length, B the width of the specimen, and Δ a correction factor.

The mode II interlaminar fracture toughness was measured in accordance to the ESIS protocol and calculated with a modified expression that accounts for the elastically asymmetric beam in the cracked region as follows:

$$G_{II} = \frac{3P\delta_{II}a^2}{2B} \left(\frac{\alpha - 2}{4L^3 + a^3(\alpha - 2)} \right) \quad (2)$$

where δ_{II} denotes the load point deflection, L the support semi-span length, and α the stiffness ratio between the full beam and the cracked arm. In the present study, $\alpha \approx 8.25$, as opposed to $\alpha = 8$ for homogeneous laminate with double symmetric layup. Eq. (2) accounts for the elastically asymmetric beams in the cracked region.

Additional details of the general procedure for manufacturing and fracture toughness testing of the different types of composite materials and the derivation of Eq. (2) were reported in our previous work [12, 13]. The delamination resistance and *in-situ* repair properties of the 3D woven composites were benchmarked against a 2D control laminate without through-thickness reinforcement. The 2D laminate was virtually identical to the 3D composites except they did not contain any z-binders.

Figure 1: Schematic of the 3D woven fabric showing the hybrid z-binder architecture.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fracture toughness properties

Fig. 2 shows the effects of using carbon and EMAA z-binder reinforcements, concurrently or separately, on the modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness properties of the 3D composites in comparison to the 2D control laminate. The 3D composite reinforced with carbon z-binder had the highest improvements to the interlaminar fracture toughness due primarily to the formation of a large-scale crack bridging zone, as shown in Fig. 3. Under mode I loading, the carbon z-binders behind the crack front initially debonded from the composite, resulting in the redistribution of the bridging traction stress along the z-binders, which caused them to fracture due to the localised geometric stress concentrations at the tight bend radii. As the crack opening displacement increased, the ruptured carbon z-binders pulled out of the 3D composite, absorbing strain energy through frictional sliding. This

bridging mechanism generates traction loads which shields the crack tip from the applied stress, thereby improving the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness. In comparison, the 3D composite containing the EMAA z-binders had a lower improvement to the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, and this is due to the lower stiffness and failure stress of the EMMA compared to the carbon z-binders.

Figure 2: Effect of z-binder material on the mode I and mode II steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness of the 2D and 3D composites.

Under mode II loading, the carbon z-binders failed along the crack bridging zone via a sequence of damage events, as shown by cross-sectional X-ray CT images of an ENF specimen in Fig. 3b. Under the action of interlaminar shear loading, the carbon z-binders begin to debond from the composite and underwent shear deformation. With increasing crack sliding displacement, splitting cracks developed within the carbon z-binders which led to their fracture. This crack bridging mechanism shielded the crack tip which increased the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon z-binder reinforced 3D composite. Similar to the carbon z-binders, the EMAA filaments formed a large-scale crack bridging zone under mode II loading, as shown in Fig. 3d. However, unlike carbon z-binders, the EMAA filaments have very low stiffness and strength, and hence they provided less resistance to delamination crack growth from their bridging action at small sliding displacements, resulting in a weaker toughening effect for this 3D composite.

Figure 3: X-ray computed tomography images showing side-views of DCB (a & c) and ENF (b & d) specimens of 3D composite containing carbon z-binders (a-b) and EMAA z-binders (c-d).

The hybrid 3D composite reinforced concurrently with carbon and EMAA z-binders showed an intermediate level of improvement to both the mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness

properties. This improvement was due to the crack bridging by the carbon and EMAA z-binders, as discussed earlier. The level of improvement to the fracture toughness of the hybrid 3D composite represented an additive toughening effect as would be expected for this material containing half the volume fraction of each type of z-binder.

3.2 Healing of z-binder reinforced composite

Healing of the delamination cracks was performed by heating the specimens at 150°C for 30 minutes, which was determined to provide the optimum healing condition for EMAA [11]. At this temperature, the EMAA melts and flows into delamination cracks via a pressure delivery mechanism unique to this type of mendable thermoplastic [11]. Upon cooling, the EMMA solidifies and bonds strongly to the pre-existing delamination surfaces. For example, Figure 4 shows cross-sectional images of a 3D composite before fracture testing (and therefore without a delamination crack), following testing (now with a long crack) and after healing (with the crack removed). The EMAA was able to infiltrate a large amount of the crack during the elevated temperature healing process and thereby heal the delamination upon cooling. Remeasuring the delamination resistance of the healed hybrid 3D composite using DCB and ENF testing revealed that the EMAA z-binders provided good healing efficiency, enabling the recovery of the mode I and mode II fracture properties of the 3D composite laminates, and the results are shown in Fig. 5. This healing process was repeatable multiple times.

A similar healing mechanism promoted by EMAA was also observed for the 3D hybrid composite reinforced with z-binders consisting of both EMAA filaments and carbon tows. However, the recovery to the mode I and II fracture toughness of the hybrid 3D composite was lower than that reinforced with EMAA only. The lower overall recovery to the fracture toughness was due to the less amount of EMAA z-binder material available for healing in this composite. This resulted in partially unhealed regions along the delamination plane.

Furthermore, the recovery to the mode I fracture toughness in the 3D hybrid composite was greater than for mode II. The healing of the cracks formed under mode I loading was more efficient because of two reasons: (i) the molten EMAA could more easily flow into the mode I delamination, which was wider and more open than the mode II crack, and (ii) the fractured ends of the carbon z-binders resisted crack growth via pull-out in the healed composites, and this did not occur under mode II loading, since the carbon z-binders had fractured close to the delamination plane, as can be seen in Fig. 3b.

Figure 4: X-ray computed tomography images of the side-view of the 3D composite containing EMAA z-binders taken (a) before delamination growth, (b) after delamination growth (with the crack visible along the mid-plane), and (c) after healing of the delamination (with the crack now removed).

Figure 5: Effect of healing cycles on the mode I and mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of the 3D composites containing EMAA z-binders, and the hybrid EMAA and carbon z-binders.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study has demonstrated the advantage of using hybrid z-binder materials on the modes I and II delamination resistance and *in-situ* repair functionality of hybrid 3D woven composites. In this composite, the carbon z-binders promoted high delamination toughness whereas the EMAA z-binders enabled mending of the delamination crack. It is possible to heal delamination cracks multiple times using the EMAA z-binders. The 3D hybrid composite material investigated here has the high delamination resistance found with conventional 3D composite materials together with the unique capability to *in-situ* repair delamination damage.

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